

ISic3290

I.Sicily inscription 3290

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 310

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---Πρ]ῖσκα [---]

2. [ἔζ]ησεν [---]

3. [ἔτ]η δέκ[α][---]

4. [έν Χρι]στῷ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Priska...lived for...years, ten... in Christ

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645557

PHI 178071

PHI 316273

PHI 336683

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1200

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 192

Libertini, G 1930. Il Museo Biscari. Milan. At 318 no.8

Ferrua, A 1938. Osservazioni sulle iscrizioni cristiane catanesi. *Bollettino Storico Catanese*. 3: 60-74. At 72 no.3

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.147

Korhonen, K. 2001. Osservazioni sul collezionismo epigrafico siciliano. *Arctos - acta philologica fennica*. 35: 85-102. At 93-94

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